

The Vordingborg Boat: Investigation, Presentation and Interpretation of a 14th-Century Boat-Find from Vordingborg Castle, Denmark

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In 2012, a mechanical excavator un-earthed the remains of a 14th-century boat while restoring the moat at Vordingborg Castle, Denmark. The boat-find was documented and both dendrochronological and metallurgical investigations were conducted. The trees that were used to build the boat were felled 1355-1366 in the region around Gdansk, Poland. However, the building of the boat was probably conducted near Vordingborg Castle in the second half of the 14th century. It is suggested that the boat was built, mainly using imported leftover materials originally intended for crafting the castle's interior features. Concluding the article, we discuss 14th-century Baltic timber trade.

Keywords: Vordingborg Castle Denmark, 14th-century boat-find, 14th-century boatbuilding, Exploitation of resources, Medieval timber trade, 14th-century Baltic power politics.

Between 2005 and 2014, local authorities in Vordingborg, Denmark and the Museum of South-East Denmark conducted the planning and construction of a new research and experience centre, *The Danish Castle Centre*, located where the remains of the medieval Vordingborg Castle are visible today. The building of the Centre comprised a construction of new buildings to house exhibitions, a museum shop and a café, and furthermore, a large-scale restoration and development project of Vordingborg Castle's historical buildings and surrounding area. Before and alongside the construction work, archaeological surveys and excavations were conducted (Annual reports from Museum of South-East Denmark, 2013 and 2014).

As part of this project, the castle moat was restored to its 14th-century layout and again filled with water. While restoring the moat's historical layout, in October 2012, a mechanical excavator dug away part of the

foreward portion of a clinker-built wooden boat (Fig. 1). Archaeological excavations of castle moats are known for resulting in remarkably well-preserved organic artefacts. In addition to their use as part of a fortification system to protect castles, moats were used as locations for depositing sewerage and other waste, and sometimes artefacts were lost and fell into the moats (Hatting, 1999: 113; Kjær and Kristensen, 1999: 311; Roesdahl, 1999: 107). Due to the many-faceted use of castle moats a wide range of artefacts are excavated, but it is not in every moat-excavation that a well-preserved boat is found.

Excavation and *in-situ* documentation

Soon after the mechanical excavator had encountered the boat, the find was excavated in a campaign stretching from October 24 and to November 15, 2012 (Fig. 2). The surviving boat components were recorded *in-situ* and subsequently recovered for more detailed post-excavation documentation (Lemée, 2013: 3-4). Archaeologist Lars Meldgaard Sass Jensen headed the overall survey and excavation campaigns and architect Christian Lemée conducted the actual excavation of the boat-find, along with archaeologist Thor Giversen. Christian Lemée subsequently wrote the report dealing with the excavation of the boat-find (Lemée, 2013).

The *in-situ* recording of the boat was done using both digital (Total Station recording) and analogue (hand drawings) methods, producing a plan of the find *in-situ* (Fig. 3) and drawings of four cross-sections. Together with numerous photographs and notes, taken as the excavation progressed, this comprised the data for writing the excavation report.

After the completion of the *in-situ* recording, all the components were recovered, one by one, marked with artefact numbers, and finally stored in water tanks in order to keep the artefacts waterlogged, until the post-excavation recording could begin.

Post-excavation documentation

Over a period of one month in the summer of 2016, the post-excavation recording of the surviving boat components was initiated. A specially designed container was placed on the castle area in Vordingborg and equipped to house both a water tank with the boat remains and space for conducting the recording of the boat-find. The Viking Ship Museum was hired to conduct the documentation with the use of the digital measuring tool, *FaroArm*, combined with the layered NURBS-based drawing programme, *Rhinoceros 3D*. The documentation was carried out at the Danish Castle Centre, so that visitors could follow the recording at close hand and this allowed the visitors to ask questions about the boat-find and the documentation method.

Many people visited the workshop, and conducting the recording under the close scrutiny of visitors was clearly a good way for disseminating the boat-find and the documentation method used. However, this way of conducting documentation is time consuming. Hence, after the month of recording, only about half of the boat components were documented.

Subsequently, both the recorded and not recorded boat components were moved from the castle area to the Museum of south-east Denmark's storage facilities in Stege on Møn. After little less than a year in water tanks, the Museum of south-east Denmark kindly asked if the Viking Ship Museum in Roskilde would be interested in taking over the boat-find, in order to complete the documentation of the find, and with a permission to later publish the boat-find. It was also to be decided whether the boat components might be included in the Viking Ship Museum's archaeological collection.

The Viking Ship Museum agreed to adopt the boat-find, and in 2017 the boat was moved from the storage facilities in Stege to the Viking Ship Museum's storage facilities in Himmelev, Zealand. In 2018, the post-excavation documentation of the boat-find, comprising of digital 3D-documentation drawings and photographs of each boat component, was completed and the process of analysing the construction and use of the boat started.

Description of the surviving boat components

In the following, we will present and discuss the shape and features of the preserved boat components. The initial observations and measurements conducted during the excavation and *in-situ* documentation are supplemented with the detailed post-excavation 3D-recording and photo-documentation of all the surviving wood components. In combination, this documentation will be used for an overall evaluation of the boat-find.

Keel

Approximately 80% of the total length of the keel is preserved in one piece: From the fragmented remains of a vertical scarf, used for joining the keel and the aft stem together, and to the broken forward end, just before the sixth frame station (Fig. 3). The preserved keel, x1123, is made of oak (*Quercus* sp.) and measures c. 274 cm in length. In cross-section the keel is T-shaped with plank-join surfaces, the so-called wings, measuring 50-55 mm. The width of the keel amidships is c. 150 mm and the thickness c. 38 mm (Fig. 4).

Toward the aft of the boat, the keel tapers into a rectangular cross-section shape with a width of *c.* 9 cm and a height of *c.* 39 mm, ending in the above-mentioned vertical scarf. In the scarf, a piece of woven textile was laid in as caulking material in order to make the scarf watertight. The fore end of the keel is likely to have a similar outline, but since this part of the keel is not preserved, this can only be assumed.

In the excavation report, a fragment from the fore part of the keel, measuring 60 cm, is mentioned (Lemée, 2013: 10). However, the keel fragment has gone missing during one of the many processes of transport and has therefore not been recorded during the post-excavation documentation (see above). It is therefore fortunate that detailed photographs of the keel fragment were taken during the excavation of the boat-find, and combined with measurements stated in the excavation report the dimensions of the fragment can be estimated to 612 mm in length, 150 mm in width and 38 mm in height (Fig. 4). Hence, the total preserved length of the keel is *c.* 335 cm.

The lower edge of the keel is much worn, and in the area where the keel is joined to the aft stem the wear and tear is likely to have resulted in the observed breaking of the scarfing (Lemée, 2013: 10-11). The damaged scarf between the keel and the aft stem has been repaired with several repair patches in the boat. Inside the boat one patch, x1073, and on the outside two more patches were nailed on. The first outer patch, x1129, was placed on the starboard side of the scarfing between the keel and aft stem, and the second patch, x1130, was placed under the area of the scarf joining the keel and aft stem. Between the inner patch, x1073, and keel-aft stem a large amount of caulking material, made from animal hair and soaked in tar, was inlaid. Furthermore, a large amount of caulking material consisting of tar-soaked felted animal hair, had been used to seal the repair from the outside by placing this material between the patch, x1130, and the underside of the scarf between the keel-aft stem area. Frequent grounding and dragging the boat ashore is likely to have caused the severe wear that can be observed on the underside of both the keel and the aft stem, and since traces of wear were also found on the outside of the repair patch, x1130, the boat had been in use some time after the repairs were conducted.

Aft stem

The aft stem is made of oak (*Quercus sp.*) and a large part of this component, x1122, is preserved: From the above-mentioned remains of the broken vertical keel-joining scarf, and to the broken upper end of the stem. While conducting the post-excavation recording it was possible to reunite two fragments, x1135a and 1135b, to the main stem part, x1122. These two fragments could be placed where the keel and aft stem were joined together, making possible a more complete recording of the vertical scarf that joins the two components.

The preserved length of the stem is *c.* 110 cm, and the excavator, Christian Lemée, has estimated the aft stem's original length to approximately 130 cm. In the upper end of the stem a drilled hole with a diameter of *c.* 25 mm is recorded (Fig. 5). This hole may have been used to moor the boat, with one rope-end fixed to the hole and the other rope-end fixed to a mooring device ashore or on a jetty. It is less likely that the hole was used for dragging the boat ashore, since the hole is placed in the aft stem. Usually dragging holes are located in the fore stem (Ravn, 2011: 296).

The joining surfaces for the run of four strakes are observed on the aft stem. The joining surfaces are carved into the aft stem allowing the hood-ends of the strakes to be fitted-in, in their full thickness, thus creating a stepped appearance. Two to three iron nails were used to join each hood-end to the joining surface, and animal hair was used as inlaid caulking material between the different components.

In the excavation report it is mentioned that the joining surfaces on starboard and port side are asymmetrical (Lemée, 2013: 13). The post-excavation documentation of the stem shows that this only concerns the joining surfaces for the second strake, that clearly are asymmetrically placed from one side to the other (Fig. 5).

Planks

All but one of the preserved planks are radially cleaved from oak (*Quercus sp.*) trunks. Only the 25 cm wide and 254 cm long oak plank, x1075, that is part of the fourth and uppermost strake on the port side, is tangentially converted.

The planks are between 17 and 25 cm wide and the thickness of the planks are between 12 and 15 mm. The length of the planks varies greatly, ranging from 78 to 283 cm. There are no decorative mouldings on the planks, and the overlap, the *land*, between the planks are between 35 and 55 mm. On the inside lower edge of the planks, grooves for caulking material have been prepared, and the caulking material inlaid in these grooves consist of twined animal hair soaked in tar. The scarfs joining the planks together longitudinally are between 12 and 15 cm long. The scarfs are terminated in different ways. Some are terminated with a lip of variable thicknesses: from a few mm up to 10 mm (in example x1125) and others terminate smoothly (in example x1128) (Fig. 6).

The planks are riveted together using iron rivets and roves. The rivet shafts have square cross-sections measuring *c.* 6x6 mm, and round rivet heads with a diameter between 25 to 30 mm. The roves are square, and can be grouped in two: some measuring 24x24 mm and others 26x36 mm (Lemée, 2013: 14). All iron fastenings are well preserved and the metallurgical analysis of 8 rivets and 3 roves are discussed in detail below.

The planking of the boat is much worn, and different repairs have been conducted in order to keep the boat afloat. The much worn inside upper edges of some planks, x1065 and x1078, have been repaired by driving in a nail from the outside through the land between the planking and subsequently double-bending the nail, driving the point of the nail into the inside of the plank. In another case, a repair patch has been riveted on the outside of the planking, x1078. Also, a repair in the port side garboard strake, near the floor timber, x1045, is made by nailing a repair patch, x1062, on the inside of the planking, after first applying tar-soaked felted animal hair, to make the repair watertight (Lemée, 2013: 14-15). Furthermore, complete planks have been replaced in the boat. On plank x1071 three cuts on the upper edge are documented (Fig. 7). These cuts are interpreted as having been made while adjusting a plank, inserted after an old plank had been replaced, attached to the floor timbers: x1046, x1047 and x1048 (Lemée, 2013: 16).

Finally, a repair has been made in the forward-most preserved plank of the fourth strake, port side. Here a repair of a split plank, x1060a-b, has been conducted by riveting a new plank, x1059, on the outside of the remaining part of the damaged plank. On the repair plank there are two treenail holes which do not penetrate the damaged plank, x1060a-b. This indicates that the plank is re-used as a repair plank and that the two non-penetrating holes are related to the plank's initial usage (Fig. 7).

Inwale

An inwale, made of beech (*Fagus* sp.), was fastened to the inside of the fourth strake on the port side. It is rectangular in shape and measures 50 mm in width and 48 mm in height amidship. Towards both ends of the boat the inwale reduces in width measuring 7 mm and with a height measuring 22 mm (Lemée, 2013: 16-17). The inwale was fastened to the planking by nails driven in from the outside of the planking, through the planking and into the inwale, and by nails again driven from the outside of the planking, but now penetrating through both the planking and the inwale and subsequently double-bending and driving the point of the nail into the inside of the inwale (Fig. 8).

Beech is not normally used for boatbuilding. It has a very low resistance to degradation in conditions with changing levels of humidity, and when fresh it can be difficult to dress with an axe. Using beech wood for the construction of the inwale may simply imply that the boatbuilders lacked more suitable raw materials. Alternatively, it may be that since an inwale is likely to be replaced, due to wear, less suited raw material may have been chosen for this component (Ravn, 2016: 56).

Just aft of the position of the floor timber, x1046, two holes, 25-27 mm in diameter, have been drilled in the upper surface of the inwale. In both holes are the remains of two treenails, which were either used as thole-pins or for fastening an oarlock to the inwale (Fig. 9). The distance between the two holes are 72 mm, and, if

the treenails are interpreted as thole-pins, this distance provides the maximum diameter of the shaft of the oars used to row the boat.

The upper edge is decomposed, and therefore no traces of wear, which would be expected if the oars were fixed between the two treenails directly on the upper surface of the inwale, could be observed. The treenails could either have been used as thole-pins or as fasteners for oarlocks. Nevertheless, the treenails and holes observed on the inwale is evidence of a rowing station in the boat situated where the floor timber x1046 is positioned.

Two more holes in the inwale, similar to the above stated, is evidence of another rowing station further aft in the boat, positioned where the floor timber x1048 is situated. In sum, the boat was propelled by the use of two pairs of oars operated by two persons seated on loosely fastened thwarts in the boat where the remains of the floor timbers x1046 and x1048 are situated (Fig. 9). No remains of these thwarts have been documented. However small grooves on the top upper side of the two floor timbers are interpreted as a possible joining surface for loosely fastened thwarts.

Floor timbers

In the excavation report it is stated that seven of the boat's original eight floor timbers are preserved (Lemée, 2013: 18-19). However, during the post-excavation recording and subsequent analysis, two of the floor timber fragments (x1043 and x1150) could be fitted together. Hence, the boat only had seven floor timbers inserted originally and the remains of all these floor timbers were preserved (Fig. 10).

On two of the floor timbers (x1046a-b and x1048) limber holes are documented (Fig. 10). It is likely that more floor timbers had limber holes, but the floor timbers' state of preservation makes it impossible to investigate this further. There are no traces of a keelson being mounted on the floor timber and no other signs of mast attachment arrangements.

The floor timbers were made of naturally-curved oak wood and were attached to the planking with treenails. The treenails were driven from the outside of the planking, and through the floor timbers and subsequently locked on the inside of the floor timbers by splinting the treenails with wedges. The wood used for crafting the treenails and wedges has not been examined. In a few cases, especially at the top ends of the floor timbers, iron nails are used as supplementary fastening. In the fore and aft end of the boat, however, the floor timbers are not connected to the garboard strake.

Interpretation of the boat-find

Based on the preserved boat components, a reconstruction 1:10 scale model was crafted. First, the *FaroArm* digitiser-generated drawings of the components were printed on paper and each element were cut around their outlines and subsequently glued onto cardboard. The cardboard planks were then fitted together to reconstruct the hull form. The planks were connected to each other with pins placed in the nail holes that originally held the planks together. The scaled versions of the floor timbers, also made of cardboard, were then fixed in the model. The scaled model of the inwale was made of wood, in order to firm the outline of the sheer (Fig. 11).

The crafting of the three-dimensional physical model enabled a reconstruction of the hull form of the original boat, and the dimensions of the boat were measured to 5.45 m in length. Midship, at floor timber x1047, the beam of the boat was measured to 1.33 m, and the height, from upper keel surface to the top of the inwale, to 0.45 m.

The distance between the frames in the boat could be measured on the scale model (Table 1). The documented treenails and holes in the inwale indicate the presence of two rowing stations at floor timber x1046 and x1048, as mentioned above (Fig. 11). The distance between these two rowing stations are 107 cm, which is sufficient space between the persons rowing the boat. The boat was propelled by oars only, operated by two persons seated at the two rowing stations, and no signs of rudder attachments are recorded. Hence, the steering of the boat was done using the oars as well. This comes as no surprise, comparable traditional Nordic small vessel types (flatners and dinghys), from the 19th and 20th centuries, were propelled and steered in a similar way (Nielsen, 1974: 68-69 and 76-77).

As already stated in the report, the overall impression of the boat-find is a much worn and heavily repaired boat, and combined with the uneven and small dimensions of most of the applied wood materials, it is probable that the boat was constructed using leftover materials originally procured for other construction projects (Lemée, 2013: 14 and 19).

Dendro analysis – dating and provenance

During the excavation, four samples were selected and later analysed (Eriksen, 2012). Three samples were from planks while the fourth was from part of the keel. However, these samples all contain relatively few tree-rings (from 40 to 69 rings) and no sapwood. At the time, only two of the samples could be dated. The estimated felling date for the trees used for building the boat was concluded to be after c. 1390 (Eriksen, 2012: 3).

Subsequently, during the post-excavation recording of the boat-find, three additional samples, all from planks, were selected and new dendrochronological analysis conducted in order to determine date and provenance (Daly, 2018). All three samples were of oak (*Quercus sp.*) and radially converted from the parent tree. It was possible to determine both date and provenance for the three samples.

The first sample, from plank x1124 (garboard strake, starboard side), contained 198 tree-rings, including nine sapwood rings. The tree-ring curve from the sample covers the period AD 1154-1351. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that the plank was made from is estimated at *c.* AD 1351-66.

The second sample, from plank x1125 (garboard strake, port side), contained 245 tree-rings. Only heartwood is preserved on this sample. The tree-ring curve from the sample covers the period AD 1103-1347, and allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date of the tree that this plank was made from is estimated at after AD 1357.

The third sample, from plank x1071 (repair plank, second strake port side), contained 199 tree-rings, including three sapwood rings. The tree-ring curve from the sample covers the period AD 1151-1349. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that this plank was made from is estimated at *c.* AD 1355-70.

Considering the high agreement, in *t*-values, between the three planks, the results might indicate that the later inserted plank was placed during the building phase of the boat or soon after. If this is taken to be the case, it can be suggested that the trees for the planks were felled between *c.* AD 1355 and 1366.

The discrepancy, in regard to felling date, between the results of the first and second dendrochronological analyses might be due to the very different quality in the sample material. In the 2012 analysis, the samples contained only 40-69 tree-rings (and no sapwood), whereas the samples analysed in 2018 contained 198-245 tree-rings and in two of the three samples even a few sapwood rings (Eriksen, 2012: 4; Daly, 2018: 1). Furthermore, when comparing the data from the first dendrochronological analysis that Eriksen kindly shared with the authors, with Northern European tree-ring datasets for oak, correlations appear for many dating positions. This is due to the very short tree-ring series, and in the light of the new analysis, where very long-lived trees from the boat are analysed and dated, producing very high and widely replicated correlations at the material's dating position, the conclusions of the first conducted analysis are here revised. Now, the 2012 samples are viewed as undated. It is thus the analysis of samples containing many more tree-rings, conducted in 2018, that is viewed as the correct felling date for the trees that were used to build the boat, *c.*

1355-1366. Just three samples are therefore dated from the boat, and thus the region of origin of the wood can only be determined for these three.

The tree-ring curves from the three dated planks display significant agreement with each other. An average of these is made. In order to determine the provenance of the trees used for building the boat, the correlation (using *t*-values) between the tree-ring curves from the three dated samples and a wide range of tree-ring datasets for oak for Northern Europe is calculated (Table 2) (for the method see e.g. Daly, 2007b; Daly and Nymoén, 2008). The distribution of the correlations is also mapped (Fig. 12). This investigation achieved highest correlation (*t*-values) with master and site chronologies for the region around the Gulf of Gdansk in today's Poland and with tree-ring data derived from archaeological finds of diverse other 14th century ships, boats and barrels that have also been shown to be made from oaks from the Lower Vistula region in Poland (Daly, 2018: 2-3).

Metallurgical analysis – provenance

The dimensions of the iron components (rivets, roves and nails) are remarkably large compared with the dimensions of the boat's wood components. The excavator, Christian Lemée, has proposed that the relatively large iron components might be explained as a use of rivets, roves and nails originally intended for a larger vessel than the Vordingborg Boat (Lemée, 2013: 14). The iron components are very well preserved and during the post-excavation recording, eleven iron artefacts, eight rivets and three roves, were sampled and metallurgically analysed, to determine the iron's chemical composition and establish the provenance of the ore used. Samples were taken either as cross-sections of the head (Fig. 13), as a longitudinal section of the rivets and as cross-sections of the roves.

In the Viking Age and the Middle Ages, iron was produced by the so-called "direct" method, in which the iron is worked to a spongy lump of wrought iron with a low carbon content. The iron can be forged directly after extraction, in contrast to the modern process in blast furnaces, where the extracted iron becomes a form of high-carbon cast iron, from which the carbon must first be removed by a refining process, before the iron can be forged.

The probable provenance of the iron was assessed by comparing analyses of slag inclusions with analyses of approximately 2500 iron smelting slags from Northern Europe. Clear differences in geology, for example, between the Northern European lowlands, the Scandinavian peninsula and central Europe, give clear chemical differences between ores, and thus between extractive slag from different areas. Most slag inclusions in iron are residues of slag from the smelting, and slag inclusions coming from other processes

can be excluded using multivariable statistical methods. The similarity between the chemical composition of slag inclusions in a piece of iron and the extraction slag from a geographical area is also assessed by multivariable statistical methods such as discriminant analysis.

All eleven artefacts were made from bog ore and, based on their chemical composition, the rivets and roves can be divided into two groups.

The first group consists of four rivets (sample numbers 1160, 1168, 1172 and 1175) all made from iron containing 0.7-0.8 % carbon and one rove (sample number 1171) with no measurable amount of carbon or phosphorous. The composition of the slag inclusions in this group are relatively homogeneous, which indicates that the rivets and rove were forged utilising iron smelted from bog ore with a similar geographical provenance. However, similarity between the analyses of the slag inclusions is not so profound that it is likely that the artefacts were made from bog ore from the same place or produced during the same smelting process (Jouttijärvi, 2018: 1-2).

When comparing the chemical composition of the slag inclusions in the rivets and rove in group one with iron smelting slags from different parts of North and Central Europe, a high degree of similarity is found with slag from the North European Plain. This area consists not least of Denmark and the northern part of Germany and Poland. However, statistically it is possible to pin down the most likely provenance of the applied bog ore even further, namely to Zealand (Fig. 14) (Jouttijärvi, 2018: 1-2). So far, the evidence of medieval iron smelting on Zealand is very limited. Only indirect evidence, like the analysis of remains of smelting slag in forged artefacts along with analysis of slags from the primary smiting (cleaning) process after the initial smelting as presented here, are to be found. However, traces of medieval iron extraction from southwestern Funen are known, where a slag heap was found in Nyvenge Forest in 1928, which, on the basis of its pottery content, dates to the 1300s (Lyngstrøm, 2013).

The second group consists of four rivets (sample numbers 1188, 1189a, 1190a and 1191) and two roves (sample numbers 1189b and 1190b). These rivets and roves are characterized as being forged from iron without a measurable amount of carbon and with a relatively high amount of phosphorous. In regard to the composition of the slag inclusions, this group of rivets and roves is not homogeneous. However, the six artefacts analysed can be divided in two subgroups: One consisting of two rivets (1189a and 1191) and one rove (1190b) which probably were forged from iron smelted using bog ore formed in Norway, and another subgroup also consisting of two rivets (1188 and 1190a) and one rove (1189b) which probably were produced using iron smelted with bog ore formed on Zealand (Jouttijärvi, 2018: 2-5).

Boatbuilding technology

The conceptual understanding behind the building of the Vordingborg Boat was shell-first; The shell (plank components) and not the skeleton (frame components) was the starting point for the design of the hull form. After the keel was laid, the stems were raised, and the hull was constructed by riveting the planks of the four strakes on each side of the boat together; lengthwise the planks were held together using short scarfs and each run of planks in a strake were joined with the adjacent strake's planks by overlapping. The garboard strake was riveted and spiked to the keel. Large amounts of animal hair, both twisted and felted, and even re-used woven textiles, were soaked in tar and used as in-laid caulking material in scarfs and lands. Only after all four strakes in each side of the plank shell had been installed were the floor timbers placed and fastened to the planking, using treenails and wedges. Finally, the inwale, the rowing related elements and other internal components were installed.

The planks were cleaved from oak logs - mostly using the radial cleaving technique and subsequently dressed with axes to ready them for the boat construction. In a few cases, tool marks have been recorded during the post-excavation documentation. On the floor timbers, x1047 and x1070, and on the plank, x1073, axe marks are visible, indicating that an axe with a small blade was used dressing these components, whereas the axe mark on plank, x1121, clearly shows that an axe with a larger blade was used for crafting this plank.

Furthermore, on the repair patch, x1062, marks after a specific axe-dressing technique, splash whittling (in Norwegian called *spret-telgjing*), is recorded. Splash whittling leaves a characteristic pattern on the timber worked, and the use of the technique can be traced back to Scandinavian construction works - including ships, churches and houses - from the 11th century and onwards (Finderup, 2006: 37-39; Thun and Storsletten, 2011).

The Vordingborg Boat's building sequence, the conceptual understanding and the applied methods and techniques are all characteristic features of the clinker boatbuilding conducted in the 14th-15th centuries in Southern Scandinavia and the Southern Baltic area. As already stated by Jan Bill, the similarities in the boatbuilding from this region in approximately 13th century and onwards are so pronounced that it might be more accurate to describe the boatbuilding as North European instead of Nordic and Slavic (Bill, 2009: 436). It is, however, possible to identify a few deviations between the small-scale, frequently built boats, in this context defined as vessels less than 10 m long, in southern Scandinavia and the southern Baltic area; Moss was mostly used as caulking material in the Baltic area, whereas animal hair was the preferred caulking material in southern Scandinavia. Another difference between the boatbuilding conducted in southern Scandinavia and the southern Baltic area are the use of fasteners to join the planks together. In southern Scandinavia iron rivets and roves were mostly used, whereas small treenails and wedges were mostly used in the southern Baltic area. These differences in the applied building methods can be traced back to the 11th

century and it seems that small-scale boatbuilding conducted in these regions followed more traditional, regionally-bound building concepts and practices throughout the Middle Ages and in some places even further (Indruszewski, 2004; Gøthche and Bill, 2006; Litwin, 2014: 31-35; Ravn, 2015).

Hence, the use of animal hair as caulking material and iron rivets and roves as fasteners alongside the above-stated applied techniques, methods and conceptual understanding, indicate that the Vordingborg Boat was built in Southern Scandinavia. Combining the results of the analysis of the metallurgical investigations of the rivets and roves, that show that the iron utilised was produced from bog ore procured mainly on Zealand, but also from Norway, we conclude that the Vordingborg Boat was built in Southern Scandinavia, most likely on Zealand. However, the provenance of some of the planks, made from trees that grew in the region around the Gulf of Gdansk, and the iron produced from Norwegian bog ore show that both locally produced and imported raw materials and primary products were used for building the boat.

In relation to this interpretation it is notable that the excavator, Christian Lemée, based on the character of the applied materials, interprets the Vordingborg Boat as having been built using leftover materials originally procured for other construction projects (see above). However, it is important to stress that the dimensions of the applied wood materials to build the Vordingborg Boat do not indicate a use of leftover materials originally intended for proper construction timbers, such as rafters, or materials intended for building larger vessels, but more likely leftover materials intended for wall planking, panels, doors and stairs, or even timbers intended for the crafting of furniture. The dimensions of the iron components, however, indicate a probable originally intended usage as fasteners for larger vessels.

During the period, the second half of the 14th century, in which the Vordingborg Boat was built, massive construction works were carried out at Vordingborg Castle (Wille-Jørgensen, 2014: 214-234). Hence, it is tempting to interpret the resources that were used for building the Vordingborg Boat as leftover materials from these construction works. If this assumption is right, the provenance of the trees used for crafting planks for the boat could also be the provenance for some of the wood raw materials and primary products used crafting part of the castle's interior features. This possible use of import, as way of procuring the materials needed, necessitates a discussion of the written and archaeological evidence of Baltic timber trade in the 14th century.

Baltic timber trade in the 14th-century

Timber trade from the Baltic area to the west is documented in written sources from the 14th century onwards. The harbour and trading town of Gdansk dominated this trade, often used for storing the wood raw materials and primary products procured probably at first in the Lower Vistula region woodlands. In Gdansk this timber was loaded onto ships for transport to other ports in Europe. The written sources describe different formats of export timbers. For example, cargoes of so-called wainscots and clapboards (staves).

From material evidence of timber cargoes and remains of oak objects of South Baltic origin, we can suggest that the wainscots were most probably planks with a length between *c.* 3-5.5 m, a width of *c.* 38 cm and a thickness between 18-37 mm. The clapboards were smaller, measuring *c.* 1.5 m in length and between 18-33 cm in width. The thickness of the clapboards was similar to the thickness of the wainscots. These relatively strictly defined dimension standards cannot be confirmed in the following discussion of the timber cargoes from contemporary ship-finds. However, since the dimensions of the wainscots and clapboards depends profoundly on the dimensions of the tree logs utilised, it is possible that the standards were followed more loosely than stated in the written evidence (Hirsch, 1858: 5-31, 83-239; Biskup, 1978; Childs, 2002; Daly, 2007b: 187-238; Auer and Maarleveld, 2013: 45-47; Ossowski, 2014b: 254-261). The evidence in the material record for this trade in fine oak boards of varying dimensions, at the time of the Vordingborg Boat, is dominated by remains of artistic and ecclesiastical works and of remains of barrels.

The Copper Ship is a 24 m long and 8 m wide clinker-built cargo ship excavated from the Gulf of Gdansk, during several campaigns between 1969-2012. The ship is dendrochronologically dated as having been built in the beginning of the 15th century (Krapiec and Krapiec, 2014: 145; Ossowski, 2014a; Zrodowski, 2014: 221). Part of the ship's cargo was recovered during the excavation campaigns; consisting of different commodities, including copper ingots, hence the naming of the ship-find: The Copper Ship (Ossowski, 2014b: 241). Among the cargo were also oak planks already worked into primary products. Two different sizes of planks were recorded; 96 have been designated as wainscots: 185-252 cm long, 185-305 mm wide and with a thickness between 15-60 mm, and as 243 staves: 540-857 mm long, 70-173 mm wide and 13-30 mm thick. Dendrochronological analysis of the cargo oak planks dated them as having been crafted using trees felled from the Gdansk, Pomerania region between 1403-1407 (Heymanowski, 1980; Krapiec and Krapiec, 2014: 147; Ossowski, 2014b: 254-258). The planks in the cargo are radially split from the parent tree, as are most of the planks used to build the ship that held this cargo. However, recent examination of the ceiling planks of the ship show that these are tangentially converted, and one even displays saw-marks.

Another contemporary ship-find with a cargo partly consisting of planks is the Skaftö ship-find, found off the coast of West Sweden, at the archipelago west of Uddevalla (some 66 km North-north-west of Gothenburg, as the crow flies). This ship-find is a clinker-built cargo ship, *c.* 25 m long and dendrochronologically dated as having been built mid-15th century (Arbin, 2009; Arbin, 2014; Arbin, 2017: 85-86). The ship's cargo consisted of different commodities such as metal and alloy ingots, bricks, tar, lime in oak barrels and oak planks. These oak planks measure 41-148 cm in length, are 150-300 mm wide and between 20 to 60 mm thick. Dendrochronological analysis of the plank cargo shows that the trees utilised for crafting the planks were felled in two regions, North and South-East Poland, in the first half of the 15th century (Arbin, 2014: 34, table 2). The barrels holding the lime cargo are also of Baltic oak (Arbin, 2014 appendix 22).

And finally, the Skjernøysund 3 ship-find should be mentioned. Skjernøysund 3 is a c. 20 m long clinker-built cargo ship dendrochronologically dated as having been built in the late part of 14th century or early part of the 15th century (Daly, 2011; Auer and Maarleveld, 2013: 40, figure 41). In addition to barrels containing lime, the ship's cargo consisted of oak planks. During the *in-situ* recording of the ship find, 35 planks were documented. Similarly to the timber cargo from the Copper Ship, the oak plank cargo from Skjernøysund 3 can be divided in two groups: Wainscots and staves. The wainscots' lengths are between 46-230 cm, the width varies between 18-26 cm and the thickness between 25-50 mm. The staves' lengths are between 26-112 cm, the width is measured to between 5-11 cm and the thickness to between 10-20 mm (Auer and Maarleveld, 2013: 25-28 and table 1). Seven of the wainscots were dendrochronologically investigated. The analysis shows that the trees utilised for crafting the planks were felled around the mouth of the Vistula River near Gdansk, in the winter 1393-1394 (Daly, 2011).

Apart from a small number of other examples of boats, from the decades around 1400, built wholly of Baltic oak, like Vejby (winter AD 1372, Bonde and Jensen, 1995), Bøle (AD 1376-96, Daly and Nymoen, 2008) and Avaldsnes (AD 1392-1410, Daly, 2007b; Alopaeus and Elvestad, 2006), we also have examples of boats that are built of a combination of wood from multiple sources, indicating transport of Baltic planks to other boatbuilding sites. Closest in time to the Vordingborg Boat is a boat found during excavations in Oslo that is dated dendrochronologically to AD 1350-62 (Daly, 2016a). For this boat, a combination of radially converted oak planks of Baltic wood and tangential planks of both oak and pine were used. Of the tangential planks, only those made of pine could be dated, indicating a Scandinavian origin. It is quite likely that this represents planks transported to Scandinavia from the South or East Baltic region.

From around AD 1419-20 another example of this has emerged. A ship found at the mouth of Greifswald Bay (Ostsee VII, Peenemündung, Fpl. 105) (Dalicsek *et al*, 2018; Steffensen, 2019) is made of oak from two sources. The planks and the framing timbers form two distinct groups: The planks correlate best with the art-historical tree-ring chronology group, so-called 'Baltic 2' (Hillam and Tyers, 1995), which appears to be from the hinterland of the Vistula river in current-day Poland. The frames however appear to be from the west Baltic, although it is not clear whether they are from the south Baltic coast or from southern Scandinavia (Daly 2019).

Three wrecks found in Copenhagen Harbour, at Dokøen, can be added to this list. The ships were excavated by the Museum of Copenhagen in 2001 (Gøthche and Høst Madsen, 2001) and dendrochronological dating of these demonstrated that all three are from the early 15th century. Wreck 2 had two felling phases at c. 1405 and c. 1425 (Eriksen, 2001a), Wreck 4 is dating to c. 1415 (Eriksen, 2001b) and Wreck 3 is from c. 1420-25 (Bonde and Eriksen, 2002; Nielsen, 2012). All three ships have timber that, through the dendrochronological analyses, show a Southern Baltic origin, but other sources of oak are also incorporated into these structures.

These three wrecks indicate transport of oak planks for shipbuilding in the early 15th century (Daly, 2007b: 220-225)

From a couple of decades later, another wreck also represents Baltic timber transported and used in a ship. The planks from the Ostsee VII Mönchgut FPL92 wreck (Stäude and Schmidt, 2011; Fiedler, 2016) were felled in winter 1448-49 and are correlating best with the 'Baltic 1' chronology group (Daly, 2010). The frames and the keel are clearly from a different source, so far not identified however.

The dimensions of the Vordingborg Boat's planks fall within the span of the dimensions of the timber cargos on board the three ship-finds, mainly in regard to the wainscots recorded from the Copper Ship and Skjernøysund 3 (Table 3). Based on the dimensions of the timber cargos it does not seem likely that wainscots and staves were originally intended for boatbuilding. A more likely intended usage of the wainscots are as materials for stairs, doors and furniture, panels for altarpieces or art or other decorative building inventory, whereas the staves might primarily have been intended for crafting barrels and other containers. However, as argued above, the Vordingborg Boat's planks might well have been produced using leftover materials originally intended for other construction works at Vordingborg Castle. Furthermore, since these planks were imported from the Gdansk region, probably as a part of a well-organized Baltic timber trade system, with Gdansk as one of the main ports, we will conclude this article with a discussion of the 14th-century power politics in the western Baltic area. This in order to explain why the Danish King, Valdemar IV (c. 1320 – 1375), might have imported building materials from Gdansk for his construction works at Vordingborg Castle.

14th-century Baltic Power Politics

In 1340, Valdemar IV was elected and proclaimed king of Denmark and, through the second half of the 14th century, Valdemar would reform and restore the kingdom's former status as an important actor on the North European scene, especially in the Baltic area. His efforts and success later earned him the nickname *Atterdag*, meaning a new dawn (Wille-Jørgensen, 2014: 214).

Valdemar IV was the youngest son of King Christopher II of Denmark (1276-1332). Under his father, Denmark became bankrupt and castles and land were pawned to noblemen from Germany and Holstein, which, in 1332, led to a total dissolution of the state. Denmark had lost its position as an important factor in the Baltic Sea. After years of negotiations between the parties involved, an agreement was reached which secured Valdemar's way to the Danish throne, in 1340, and step-by-step he managed to redeem and unite the rest of the kingdom. When the money ran out, he used force and his army to achieve his goals. The funding came from extra taxes paid by Danish peasants and from the sale of Estonia, in 1346, to the Teutonic Order

when Valdemar gave up the dream of a Danish empire in the Baltic (Etting, 2010: 32-33). The importance and strategic role of Vordingborg in this process is apparent, in that it was the first castle that Valdemar tried to gain control over, after he became king in 1341. However, this was not successful until five years later, in 1346, when he succeeded in regaining Vordingborg (Olsen, 1981: 32-34).

Soon after Valdemar IV came in possession of Vordingborg, the castle was completely rebuilt and became the largest and most important royal castle in Denmark, in the second half of the 14th century. The new Vordingborg was a strong, state-of-the-art fortress with an inner and outer castle, both surrounded by strong curtain walls and an outer moat filled with water manipulated through complex hydraulic systems. The castle contained the royal archives, the royal treasury, the king's chancellery and a chapel probably intended to hold the king's tomb, where he was buried in 1375. This shows that the castle was probably intended to be a more permanent residence and to serve as an expression of the king's ambitions in the western Baltic Sea Region (Bracke, 1999: 44-45; Wille-Jørgensen, 2014: 226-240). A number of dendrochronological datings from construction timbers still preserved in the Goose Tower and from the excavation of the moat, in 2012, suggests that building took place from the late 1350s until the mid-1360s (Christensen, 1998; Bonde and Brandstrup, 2013). Several royal castles on Zealand were rebuilt and enlarged during this period, which served to enforce the Crown's power. In the Chronicle of Zealand, it is mentioned that the royal castles, between 1351-1358, were undergoing great changes and became surrounded by moats (Olsen, 1981: 36-52). Dendrochronological datings from the royal castles Kalundborg and Gurre show that major earthworks and rebuilding were done between 1356-1365 and both with significant watery landscapes in the same way as in Vordingborg (Hertz, 1990: 87; Etting, 2010: 152-167; Etting, Hvass and Boje Andersen, 2003: 23, 75, 89). This indicates that the great restoration and expansion of the royal castles took place from the beginning of the 1350s until the mid-1360s and was finished or nearly finished before the first war between Valdemar and the Hanseatic League.

These construction works were enormous and required large amounts of bricks, lime for mortar and building timbers. Denmark was apparently not particularly short of bulk construction timber in the 14th-century and there are some indications that the wooded areas generally increased in this period. For the same reason, the import of building timber did not become extensive in this period (Hybel and Poulsen, 2007: 13-23). The provenance of the construction timber used in Gurre and Vordingborg for larger construction works and buildings shows that timber from Zealand, Lolland-Falster and Scania were used (Christensen, 1998; Bonde and Brandstrup, 2013; Eriksen, 2000; Eriksen, 2001c; Eriksen, 2003). Although there are some sites in Denmark, e.g. the moated site at Boringholm, from 1370s-1380s, that was built of local oaks, but here, relatively young trees were utilised (Daly 2005; Daly, 2007b: 206-212). At Boringholm, remains of several barrels made from Baltic oak staves, demonstrate the new emergence of the trade in this material by the late 14th century. The Vordingborg Boat might indicate that Valdemar IV imported timber from Gdańsk to his

new castle in Vordingborg, intended for crafting stairs, doors, wall planking and furniture, panels for art or other decorative building inventory, and for building barrels and other containers. The fine, straight-grained oaks from the Southern Baltic region, converted into planks, boards, clapboards etc, as we have seen used in shipbuilding and in the rare cases where ships with wood cargo have been found, began to be traded to Western Europe from the mid-14th century. Barrels made of staves of Baltic oak appear even earlier (Daly, 2007b: 177-179). This, of course, raises the question of whether import of boards from the Southern and eastern Baltic had already become a widespread phenomenon in relation to Valdemar IV's castle building, in the 1350s to the mid-1360s.

In 1361 and again in 1367, Valdemar IV was at war with the Hanseatic League and the western Hanseatic towns under Lübeck's leadership, which may have influenced his ability to import timber from Gdansk (Etting, 2010: 34-35). Besides being a member of the Hanseatic League, Gdansk was under the control of the Teutonic Order and stood in opposition to Valdemar in his conflict with the western Hanseatic towns, though did not take an active part (Śliwiński and Możejko, 2017: 26-29). Nevertheless, the consequence for the Danish king may have been that it was impossible to import timber directly from Gdansk. That wars could lead to these kinds of restrictions is known from the war between England and the Hanseatic League, in 1469-1474, where the trade in timber had to re-route over neutral cities or countries (Ważny and Eckstein, 1987: 512). If this was the case, a trade ban would not have come into effect before 1361 and subsequently under normal circumstances, the Danish King would hardly have been able to import large quantities of Baltic boards directly from Gdansk for his castle construction after this year.

Valdemar IV's connections to the Teutonic Order might have provided him with a possibility to procure the wood resources needed for the considerable construction works at Vordingborg Castle also during the wars with the Hanseatic League. The relationship between the two Baltic powers was not particularly intense, as their spheres of interest did not overlap. Denmark's main interest was the western half of the Baltic Sea, while the Teutonic Order was the eastern half and only in a few places had common political interests such as Gotland and Estonia (Herrmann, 2009: 119). During the time of the sale of Estonia, in 1346, Valdemar was in close contact with the Teutonic Order through his diplomats. Most of the negotiations took place at Marienburg less than 60 km south of Gdańsk where the Grand Master of the Teutonic Order had his residence (Christensen, 1959; Tägil, 1962: 128-137). Later that year, Valdemar travelled via Lübeck to Prussia to take part in crusades against the Lithuanians, this together with the Teutonic Order. During his stay, he went from castle to castle and had the opportunity to see and experience some of the most modern fortifications around the Baltic Sea. The crusade was never completed but the king had time to strengthen diplomatic and personal relations (Herrmann, 2009: 123-124; Jørgensen, 1911: 126-127; Paravicini, 1989: 148). The following year Valdemar's older brother Otto of Denmark (*c.* 1310 – after 1346) was admitted to the Teutonic Order and renounced the claim to the Danish throne (Fenske and Militzer, 1993: 493-194). In

that way, Valdemar got rid of a competitor to the throne and established strong and close familial connections to a powerful actor in the eastern Baltic Sea Region. This might also have secured the possibility for imports of timber even during times of war. The small, and at first sight insignificant, Vordingborg Boat has shown an important potential for investigating the beginning of what subsequently became an enormous trade of fine straight-grained oak boards, that dominated the timber trade across Northern Europe, for several centuries.

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Tables

	Frame-spacing (in cm)
From the aft stem to frame 7	<i>c.</i> 86
From frame 7 to frame 6	<i>c.</i> 67
From frame 6 to frame 5	<i>c.</i> 56
From frame 5 to frame 4	<i>c.</i> 63
From frame 4 to frame 3	<i>c.</i> 44
From frame 3 to frame 2	<i>c.</i> 50
From frame 2 to frame 1	<i>c.</i> 57
From frame 1 to the fore stem (not preserved)	<i>c.</i> 96 (est)

Table 1. Frame-spacing measured from the centre of one floor timber to the next. Since part of the fore-body is missing, the spacing between frame 1 and the fore stem is estimated. (Morten Ravn, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Filenames	-	-	Average 3 planks Z219M001	
-	start	dates	AD 1103	
-	dates	end	AD 1351	
Master and site chronologies				
P671001m	AD 980	AD 1347	11.08	Poland, Elblag (Ważny, pers comm)
PM670108	AD 725	AD 1985	10.91	Poland, Gdansk (Ważny, pers comm)
PP125M01	AD 917	AD 1400	9.56	Poland, Elblag 150 timbers (Ważny, pers comm, revised Daly 2007b)
PP124M01	AD 982	AD 1356	9.18	Poland, Elblag 120 timbers (Ważny, pers comm, revised Daly 2007b)
DM200005	AD 915	AD 1873	8.64	Germany, Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni.)
DM200006	AD 914	AD 1873	8.43	Germany, Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni.)
PP114M01	AD 1152	AD 1447	8.29	Poland, Gdansk Wole, 18 timbers (Ważny, pers comm, revised Daly 2007b)
P676001m	AD 1084	AD 1393	7.96	Poland, Kolobrzeg (Ważny, pers comm)
G1101Z03	AD 1124	AD 1319	7.81	Germany, Flensburg, 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni., revised Daly 2007b)
PP106M01	AD 1110	AD 1399	7.71	Poland, Gdansk Parc. 6, 14 timbers (Ważny, pers comm, revised Daly 2007b)
G350PZ01	AD 967	AD 1381	7.32	Germany, Truhen, 46 timbers (Göttingen Uni., revised Daly 2007b)
DM100010	AD 1023	AD 1723	7.29	Germany, Lübeck (Hamburg Uni.)
0676001S	AD 1067	AD 1305	7.18	Poland, Kolobrzeg, 7 timbers (Ważny, pers comm)

Ships, boats and barrels				
Z0952M01	AD 1190	AD 1345	11.04	Barcode boat 17, BC17, Norway, 2 timbers (Daly 2016a)
D0132M02	AD 1096	AD 1336	10.93	Odense, Thomas B Thriges barrel staves, 7 timbers (Daly 2016b)
CLS2000	AD 1110	AD 1393	9.36	Hull, Chapel Lane, Yorkshire, 11 boat planks (Tyers, pers comm)
CD40UZ03	AD 1102	AD 1351	9.32	Svendborg, Brogade/Gåsetorvet, (boat) 2 timbers (Nationalmuseet, revised Daly 2007b)
HMC_T165	AD 1078	AD 1369	9.28	Hull boards from 37 coffins, Yorkshire (Tyers, pers comm)
Z005M003	AD 1063	AD 1373	8.88	Norway, Bølevraget, planks, 4 timbers (Daly and Nymoen 2008)
0045M002	AD 1109	AD 1370	8.67	Vejby skib, 18 trees (Bonde and Jensen 1995)
se617M01	AD 1100	AD 1396	8.52	New Baxtergate Grims., 5 timbers (Sheffield Uni., revised Daly 2007b)
doel1_repai...	AD 1142	AD 1281	8.18	Doel 1,_ship timbers, repair (Haneca and Daly 2014)
doel1_all_m2	AD 1150	AD 1305	7.72	Doel 1, ship timbers, (Haneca and Daly 2014)
0056M001	AD 1174	AD 1335	7.46	Aberdeen barrel (Crone, pers comm)
02071M01	AD 1126	AD 1414	7.29	Copenhagen, Dokøen, Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001a)
P0011009	AD 1103	AD 1403	7.26	Gdansk, Copper Ship, wainscots (Ważny, pers comm)

Table 2. Vordingborg Boat. Result of the correlation between the average curve for the dated samples (Z219M001) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values. (Aoife Daly, Research Project TIMBER, University of Copenhagen)

	Felling dates (dendro)	Length (in mm)	Width (in mm)	Thickness (in mm)
Vordingborg Boat, planks	Ship: c. 1351-66	780-2830	170-250	12-15
Copper Ship, timber cargo	Ship: 1398-1400 Plank cargo: 1403-1407	Wainscots: 1850-2520 Staves: 540-857	Wainscots: 185-305 Staves: 70-173	Wainscots: 15-60 Staves: 13-30
Skaftö, timber cargo	Ship: late 1430s Plank cargo: c. 1440-43	410-1480	150-300	20-60
Skjernøysund 3, timber cargo	Ship: 1387-90 Plank cargo: winter 1393-94.	Wainscots: 460-2300 Staves: 260-1120	Wainscots: 180-260 Staves: 50-110	Wainscots: 25-50 Staves: 10-20

Table 3. Dimensions of planks from the Vordingborg Boat and of the timber cargos from the Copper Ship, Skaftö and Skjernøysund 3. The planks from the Vordingborg Boat are much worn, and thus the thickness of the planks was probably greater when the boat was new. (Morten Ravn, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Figures

Figure 1: Location map. (Lars Meldgaard Sass Jensen, Aarhus University)

Figure 2: Scenes from the excavation of the boat and the recovery of the boat components. (Museum of Southeast Denmark)

Figure 3: General plan of the Vordingborg Boat *in situ*. The frame stations are numbered from the fore end to the aft end of the boat. (Christian Lemée, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Figure 4: The keel, x1123, and the fore-end keel fragment reunited with the rest of the preserved keel. (Tom Nicolajsen, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Figure 5: The aft stem, x1122, and the two fragments, x1135a-b, that were reunited with the main part of the aft stem. (Tom Nicolajsen, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Figure 6: Scarf types used for joining planks together. Top: a short scarf that terminates smoothly. Bottom: a longer scarf that terminates with a lip. The two drawings do not show plank scarfs from the Vordingborg Boat, instead they are principle drawings. (Morten Gøthche, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Figure 7: Plan of the preserved planks and the keel. Note the three cuts on the upper edge of x1071 interpreted as an adjustment conducted while replacing an old plank with a new one. Another example of a repair is seen on the split plank x1060a-b. Here, a new plank, x1059, is riveted on the outside of the damaged plank. The plan also shows the timber and iron samples selected for dendrochronological and metallurgical analyses. (Tom Nicolajsen, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Figure 8: Detail photograph from the excavation, showing a double-bent nail. (Christian Lemée, Museum of Southeast Denmark)

Figure 9: Detail photograph from the excavation, showing two holes and the remains of two treenails, either used as thole-pins or fastening of an oarlock. (Christian Lemée, Museum of Southeast Denmark)

Figure 10: Plan of the preserved floor timbers. All the floor timbers are seen looking towards the fore end of the boat. Note the two floor timbers (x1046a-b and x1048) with limber holes. Limber holes are openings on the underside of a floor timber which allow water inside the boat to circulate and reach the bailing area of the boat. (Tom Nicolajsen, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Figure 11: Reconstruction 1:10 scale model of the Vordingborg Boat. Note the two rowing stations at floor timbers x1046 and x1048. The model was crafted by Vibeke Bischoff. (Morten Ravn, Viking Ship Museum, Roskilde)

Figure 12: Map showing the distribution of the correlations (t -value) for the planks from the Vordingborg Boat. The larger the dot, the higher the t -value. For details of the method, see e.g. Daly (2007b). The river data is from Lehner and Grill (2013, www.hydrosheds.org, accessed 3rd March 2020). (Aoife Daly, Research Project TIMBER, University of Copenhagen)

Figure 13: Cross section from the head of a rivet from the Vordingborg Boat. (Arne Jouttijärvi, Heimdal-archaeometry, Virum)

Figure 14: Comparing the chemical composition of the slag inclusions in the rivets and rove in group one with iron smelting slags from the northern part of Germany and Poland and Zealand. (Arne Jouttijärvi, Heimdal-archaeometry, Virum)